

SPECIFIC PRAGMATIC LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF SOCIO-POLITICAL TEXTS

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Abstract. In this article, we will examine the main problems that arise when interpreting socio-political texts. This analysis is intended to shed light on the difficulties associated with this type of interpretation and to provide insight into potential strategies for solving these problems.

Keywords: Translation, pragmatic aspect, socio-political texts, interpreters, political speech, Complex Terminology and Concepts, Linguistic Ambiguity and Multilingualism.

Socio-political speeches and texts are often used by politicians to convey their messages or views to the public. Political texts can also be used as a tool for persuasion or giving instructions from a politician to the general public.

In relation to translation, interpreting socio-political texts can undoubtedly present a number of difficulties due to several factors, one of which is that political speech is considered a special text genre, that is, it has unique properties that other text types may not have. Another factor that increases the complexity of translating political speeches is the close connection of political speech with socio-political aspects. For example, many political speeches in Indonesia begin with religious greetings from religions such as Islam, Christianity, Hinduism, Buddhism, and Confucianism that are officially recognized in Indonesia. This can be considered a unique feature of Indonesian political discourses that is not found in political discourses in other countries. A few Indonesian texts may have a pantun or traditional Indonesian poetic

form, usually at the end of a speech. Translating these features into other languages can cause translation problems and difficulties.

In addition, translators who have to translate political speeches are also required to be aware of all issues related to political traditions or customs in a particular country, as this will help them in the translation process. For example, a translator translating a political speech from Uzbek to English should know the common phrases used as greetings and salutations in Uzbek political speeches, as well as how to find their common equivalents in English and when to choose the right strategy.

Since political discourses discuss various topics, they often include terms from different fields such as history, cultural studies, religious studies, etc. Therefore, it becomes difficult for interpreters or translators to translate these speeches.

Given the unique nature and complexity of socio-political texts described above, translating political texts can present unique challenges to translators and interpreters. For this purpose, this study aims to study the most suitable translation method that can be adopted for the oral translation of socio-political texts. A loosely defined translation method is a translator's approach to the text to be translated.

In order to deliver political texts without any mistakes, the translator must have pragmatic knowledge, the content of the translated text, theories of translation, and a number of qualities that a translator must have. Adequacy and equivalence are theories they must know. To ensure the high quality of the translation, the translator must be able to compare the translated text with the original, assess and classify possible errors, and make necessary corrections.

Different classifications of translation problems have been proposed by translation theorists and scientists based on their perceptions of how the translation process is carried out and what problems and difficulties arise in this process. One of the main figures working with functionalist approaches to translation is Christina Nord, who argues, "Translation problems can be pragmatic, cultural, linguistic, or text-specific." Below, we consider potential strategies for dealing with the problems encountered in interpreting sociopolitical texts.

1. Cultural Nuances and Contextual Understanding: One of the primary challenges in interpreting socio-political texts is navigating the cultural nuances embedded in the content. Socio-political texts often contain references to historical events, cultural practices, and societal norms that may not be immediately apparent to interpreters from different cultural backgrounds.

2. Complex Terminology and Concepts: Socio-political texts frequently contain complex terminology and concepts that require specialized knowledge to interpret accurately.

3. Linguistic Ambiguity and Multilingualism: Socio-political texts are often characterized by linguistic ambiguity, where words and phrases can have multiple meanings depending on the context in which they are used. Interpreters must possess a high level of linguistic proficiency in both the source and target languages to accurately navigate these ambiguities and convey the intended meaning of the text.

4. Time Sensitivity and Dynamic Nature of Content: Socio-political texts are often time-sensitive and subject to rapid changes due to evolving political developments, social movements, and current events. Interpreters working with socio-political texts must be able to respond quickly to these dynamic changes and adjust their interpretation strategies accordingly.

5. Interpretation of Complex Ideas: Socio-political texts often deal with complex ideas and theories that require careful interpretation and explanation. Translators need to have a strong grasp of the subject matter to accurately interpret these concepts in another language.

6. Ethical Considerations and Professional Standards: Interpreting socio-political texts raises ethical considerations related to confidentiality, privacy, and professional standards. Interpreters must adhere to strict ethical guidelines to protect the integrity of the interpretation process and maintain the trust of all parties involved.

To tackle these issues, the translator must meet the following requirements:

1. Complete familiarization with the topic discussed in the original text;
2. Knowing the original language and its lexical-grammatical features well enough compared to the mother tongue;

3. Knowing the basics of translation theory, as well as translation techniques and their use;

4. A clear understanding of the essence of the scientific and technical functional method both in the original language and in the mother tongue;

5. Familiarization with accepted symbols, abbreviations, system of measurements and weights, etc., both in the original language and in the native language;

6. Good knowledge of mother tongue and correct use of terms.

The examination of key aspects, ranging from the importance of oral translation in socio-political texts to the nuanced considerations involved in conveying meaning, preserving persuasiveness, bridging cultural differences, and fostering diplomatic relations, underscores the complexity and significance of oral translation in shaping global discourse. Furthermore, the exploration of theoretical frameworks and the incorporation of case studies contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities and implications associated with oral translation in socio-political contexts.

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